

INTRODUCTION

Submitted by MELISSA CASTILLO NAPIL on 08.08.2024.

A thesis is a form of academic writing which is a common requirement in completing a degree. It comprises research articles that have been explored in many academic studies. Accordingly, since the introduction comes after the abstract in a research paper, it is one of the most important sections. (Alharbi, 2021). The researcher observed that every specialization in the College of Teacher Education (C.T.E.) at the University of Mindanao (U.M.) has a different structure on how this must be constructed and organized. This raises concerns among students who are doing undergraduate research as they observe that every research panelist, teacher, and adviser has different views on how the research must be structured. Through a genre analysis, researchers will attempt to provide a complete view of the rhetorical structure of undergraduate research across various specializations.

As emphasized in the study of Ono and Petric (2022), writing a thesis has become a difficult undertaking for universities in Pakistan; despite seminars, workshops, and symposiums held, the researchers found that research writers are not fulfilled. Furthermore, most Pakistani universities have no published guidelines for writing research-related genres like theses, dissertations, and research articles, which would aid students in developing their academic writing abilities.

Subsequently, writing a thesis has become a challenging task for Pakistani Universities; despite seminars, workshops, and symposiums conducted, the researcher observed that researchers are not fulfilled to a greater extent. Additionally, there are no published guidelines available in most of the universities in Pakistan for writing research genres such as research articles, theses, and dissertations that would help them improve their academic writing skill (Ono and Petric, 2022),.

The result of their study showed that the thesis published has no convention of consistency and found that six theses have no introduction to their conducted study. A research introduction is critical since it serves as a window to the reader and determines whether the reader must continue reading the research article. The study's background, problem statement, objective, significance, limitations or delimitations, and operational definitions are all included in the introduction section. (Afshar, Doosti, & Movassagh, 2018).

In addition, Yasmin, Mahmood, and Butt (2019), a research introduction is where the topic and approach will be presented with several goals, such as presenting a topic, getting the reader's interest, providing background, positioning your approach, detailing the research problem, and giving an overview of paper's structure. Additionally, they outline the steps for the research introduction, which include introducing the topic, outlining the background, defining the research problem, making connections to the literature, outlining your objectives, and organizing your paper.

The Creating a Research Space (C.A.R.S.) model was first presented by John Swales in 1990. It is a framework for analyzing journal articles that span

a range of discipline-based writing styles. Since then, a great deal of research on academic writing has examined Swales's work on the move structure of research article structure and genre-analysis in the introduction, garnering scholarly attention. John Swales presented the CARS Model in response to criticism that writing an introduction for a research paper is difficult and problematic.

Furthermore, this aims to elucidate and depict the structure of composing the introduction to academic research papers. According to Afshar, Doosti, and Movassagh (2018), Swales developed methods and procedures for examining the genre analysis and textual structure of research articles across a range of academic fields. The research article introduction is said to consist of three moves, according to Swales' CARS model: move one defines a territory, move 2 creates a niche, and move 3 occupies the niche. Every move is required and optional (Kafes, 2018).

Nonetheless, a number of studies that have been carried out in response to Swales' CARS model have suggested certain adjustments and modifications. According to recent studies, the structure and a few key elements of different introductions were not sufficiently taken into account by the rhetorical structure of the moves in Swales' CARS model. Elevating doubts about the CARS model's applicability and highlighting the need for more adjustment and integration in order to take into account the structures present in research article introductions across disciplines (Jam, 2020).

On the other hand, the CARS model is used and applied in different fields in different languages to analyze the genre of the research abstracts and

introductions in graduate and post-graduate theses. In addition, Kalali and Kian (2015) mentioned that the Swales Model is worth it because it focuses on the cognitive schemata that emphasize the shared Purpose as a well-communicative event and as the indispensable element of any genre of research.

In Prasetyanti and Tongpoon-Patanasorn's (2023) studies, the Swales CARS Model was applied. It was discovered that the majority of the research introductions for the non-English research did not address Move 2, which is creating a niche in the CARS Model. This implies that their analyzed genre introduction researched does not follow the CARS Model of John Swales, while an investigation carried out by Afshar et al. (2018) revealed that there is a high percentage of adhering to CARS Model considering the patterns and recurrence of moves, steps, and sub-steps while giving attention to the linguistic features contributed to the reliability of the results obtained through genre analysis on research articles.

Every communication in general and academic writing texts is considered to require genre analysis, which is the study of situated language in a specific context. Moreover, pursuing a common rhetorical pattern for producing an academic text has recently been mandated as a requirement for graduating students. Numerous scholars have suggested comprehensive elucidations of the rhetorical structures of distinct sections of scholarly texts, and a substantial body of literature has been devoted to examining various academic genres, including research articles, theses, and dissertations written in English (Shirani & Chalak, 2018).

Swales (1990) defined a genre as a communicative sequence of events with a particular objective for genre practitioners to accomplish. The genre expresses rhetorical and textual characteristics that are positioned by the genre itself as well as in the context, which also establishes the standards for genre usage. Therefore, genre is a type of social action that sets common features.

These features developed certain genre families, such as research genres, which include research articles, theses/dissertations, conference presentations, and ensuing proceedings. These genres are highly identical to one another, both textually and rhetorically. Common structural components of research genres include the abstract, introduction, literature review, research methodology, result and discussion, and conclusion. These structural units, also known as part-genres, are further distinguished by the text's schematic patterns of lexicon-grammatical and rhetorical elements. The method of genre analysis is used to examine the textually and rhetorically schematized patterns of these subgenres (Suherdi, Kurniawan, & Lubis, 2020).

In the Philippines, genre analysis still needed to be well-known for research, especially the CARS Model as a framework for writing introductions. Lintao and Erfe (2015) attempt to comprehend profession-based academic writing in two distinct cultural contexts by applying the Swales Model. They concluded that more than a limited number of corpora is required to be used in a genre analysis.

In the local set-up, Davao City, Porras, and Ingilan (2017) conducted genre analysis in Applied Linguistics in 12 research introductions. Their research shows that Move One and Move Three claimed to have 100% of

occurrences, and the most notable difference is the absence of Move 2, which claims only to have 58% of the occurrences. Then, the researcher concluded that the framework provided by Swales “was meant to describe, not to prescribe.” In addition, some moves are obligatory since they are an essential part of a research introduction.

Based on researchers’ observation of the curricula of teaching research at the university, particularly in the C.T.E., the CARS Model was not included as a framework for writing a research introduction. Even the researcher confirms that in the past, written research CARS model was not followed. Hence, the study aims to investigate the rhetorical structure of the research introduction article in the UM CTE. Specifically, it sought to describe the characteristics of the UM CTE thesis introduction and to determine the non-conformance by utilizing the CARS Model.

The investigation's outcome may provide writing teachers and students in U.M. with valuable and relevant information concerning how a genre is constructed in a particular context of the research. The outcome of this study may have some meaningful implications in guiding students to become more effective writers in research. Further, this study may provide a better understanding of how student -researchers formulate their introductions and create standards through guidelines to assist students in their formulation of introductions, and the study may provide future researchers with guidelines for formulating a practical introduction through findings in this study.

METHOD

Research Corpora

The researchers employed purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling technique. Since the researchers' judgment is what determines the sample size in this sampling method, there is no mathematical computation involved. (Nikolopoulou, 2023; Office of the Auditor General of Canada, 2019). A total of 20 introductions from the undergraduate theses of UM CTE of the academic year 2017-2020 were selected because they fulfilled the characteristics that the study needs, and the researchers want to concentrate in depth utilizing small samples (George, 2023).

The selected introductions are homogeneous sampling because they share commonalities in their study, which centers on humanities, social sciences, pedagogy, and language (Glen, 2023). The college programs were Bachelor in Secondary Education (B.S.E.D.), specializing in Filipino, English, and Social Studies. The other college programs such as BSED Math, General Science, SNED, ECED and BEED were excluded for the reason the researchers aimed of a homogenous sampling.

Materials and Instrument

This research utilized these outputs: laptops, papers, and pens. The theses are the source of the text data analyzed using genre analysis. Laptops are used to type inputs regarding the analysis of data collected from the introduction. Paper and pens were used to note necessary information throughout the research procedures. The number of occurrences of three

moves with steps and sub-steps of the CARS Model was used to evaluate the undergraduate thesis introduction.

Design and Procedure

This study also utilized descriptive-qualitative research employing genre analysis. According to Doyle (2020), a descriptive-qualitative study mainly focuses on the description rather than examining relationships or associations. This attempts to explore the characteristics of the research introductions of C.T.E. undergraduate theses using genre analysis instead of explaining the phenomenon's underlying causes or mechanisms (Seixas et al., 2018). Academic content can be analyzed on both a macro and micro level using genre analysis.

At the micro level, researchers focus on specific grammatical or lexical features used in writing. While at the macro level, researchers work with the rhetorical patterns of the academic content in different disciplines (Yin, 2018). This aims to provide a detailed description of the rhetorical structure of introductions of randomly selected theses of UM CTE using genre analysis through John Swales's Creating a Research Space model (1990). Swales's model is used to examine introduction data to discover and identify its characteristics and non-conformance sections of the C.T.E. thesis introductions based on the CARS Model.

Consequently, the researchers obtained permission from the panel members to conduct the study, which was done during the title defense. They conferred the panel on which particular programs were selected for the respondents of the study. They also obtained inputs on which model to use as

an analysis tool for the course of the study and decided to apply the Swales Model as the method of analysis. Taking all the panels' comments into consideration, the researchers asked for authorization for C.T.E. to conduct the study, and it was approved and signed by the Dean. After the approval of the letter of consent, the researchers gathered the undergraduate thesis introduction from the selected programs of the UM CTE. Following that, the researchers gathered the research introductions from undergraduate students. The duration of this was taken from April 2021 to April 2022. After that compilation, the researchers then used the Swales Model as a tool for showing the different characteristics of the thesis introduction.

The data that the researchers gathered have been processed and analyzed using John Swales, creating a research space model that consists of three moves. Move 1, establishing the territory, which consists of three steps:

Showing centrality (divided into four subcategories: by topic, by interest, by importance, by a standard procedure), making topic generalizations, and reviewing previous studies. Move 2 is establishing a niche, which consists of only one step that is divided into four: counterclaiming, indicating a gap, question-raising, and continuing a tradition. Move 3, occupying a niche, consists of four steps: outlining the Purpose and announcing the present research, announcing the main findings, indicating the structure of the article, and evaluating the findings (Shirani & Chalak, 2018).

Nonetheless, the thesis writers and advisers, including the thesis title, are anonymous and confidential. In addition, all data collected were handled with respect and confidentiality, and the process of analysis will be done not according to the desired outcome of the researchers but towards the authentic

evaluation based on the standards of the model followed. This study's approaches regarding objectivity and trustworthiness were credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability.

Figure 1: Model Procedure of the CARS Model

The researchers followed Levitt's major principles in ethical research: privacy and animosity, confidentiality, informed consent, rapport, intrusiveness, and data interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 20 thesis introductions were analyzed in the study which included: 9 Filipino, 8 English, and 3 Social Studies unpublished from the school year 2017 to 2020.

Table 1 shows the three moves in the UM CTE Thesis Introductions. The three moves of Swales' (1990) CARS Model were used in the research introductions. *Move 1 Establishing a Territory* has 20 occurrences or 41.66%;

Table 1
Frequency of the Steps on each Move on CARS Model

Moves and Steps		Steps		Moves	
		f	%	f	%
Move 1 Establishing a Territory				20	41.66
Step 1	Claiming Centrality	4	6.56	-	-
Step 2	Topic Generalizations	16	26.23	-	-
Step 3	Reviewing Items from Previous Research	17	27.89	-	-
Move 2 Establishing a Niche				8	16.66
Step 1A	Counterclaiming	1	1.64	-	-
Step 1B	Indicating a gap	1	1.64	-	-
Step 1C	Question Raising	-	-	-	-
Step 1D	Continuing a Tradition	6	9.83	-	-
Move 3 Occupying a Niche				20	41.66
Step 1A	Outlining the Purposes	-	-	-	-
Step 1B	Announcing Present Research	9	14.75	-	-
Step 2	Announcing Principal Findings	6	9.83	-	-
Step 3	Indicating R.A. Structure	-	-	-	-
		60	100%	48	100%

Move 2 Establishing a Niche with eight occurrences or 16.66%; and *Move 3 Occupying the Niche* with 20 occurrences or 41.66%. The total of occurrences of moves is 48, as identified in all the corpora, and there are 60 occurrences in a total of steps in all corpora.

It also showed 37 occurrences in total for the steps in Move 1, Establishing a Territory; *Step 1, Claiming centrality*, had four occurrences or 6.56%; *Step 2, Topic Generalization*, had 16 occurrences or 26.23%; and *Step 3: Review Items from Previous Research* with 17 or 27.89%.

Move 1: Establishing a Territory

All analyzed research introductions have occurred with Move 1 Establishing a Territory, where the research writer declares the topic of the study as significant and interesting (Otugen, et al., 2021). Researchers established the research area well while following the steps in this move. In some introductions Move 1 is used cyclically (two or three times in the texts), but all these introductions start with Move 1 as well.

Move 1: Step 1- Claiming Centrality

According to the CARS Model showing centrality, the writers must state the importance or relevance of the research topic, such as presenting the topic in a way that is useful, this move is known as optional (Alharbi, 2021) if it appears less than 60% of the corpus, since of 20 research introductions analyzed, there were only four introductions that contained Step 1 from Move 1.

Examples:

*“Ang pag-aaral na ito ay nagsasaliksik ng mga mag-aaral sa “Paggamit ng Internet at Facebook” pati na rin kung paano ang paggamit nito at mga pananaw tungkol sa akademikong epekto ng paggamit, ito ay may kaugnayan sa oras na ginugol sa pag-aaral o akademikong pagganap.”
(Fil2020-1)*

"This study explores students' " Use of the Internet and Facebook" as well as how its use and perceptions about the academic impact of use it is related to the time spent on student or academic performance"

"Ang mga Gawain tulad ng pagiging hindi handa sa klase, pakikipag-usap sa klase, pakikipaglaban, pandaraya, kawalang-galang sa mga guro, at iba pa ay maaring makagambala sa proseso ng pagtuturo at pag-aaral (Fil2020-2).

"Activities such as being unprepared in class, talking in class, fighting, cheating, disrespecting teachers, and others may disrupt the teaching and learning process"

In this part, it is necessary that the written research must provide a link from previous studies to current, wherein in this study, only four introduction theses contained this step, which could have been due to the difficulty in choosing the research area and assessing the scope of the research zone (Suherdi, et al.,2020). Moreover, to demonstrate conformity with the thesis's scope, move one was reiterated, and authors were encouraged to make their work more engaging, lively, and relevant to the field (Hussain, Hussain & Asif Khan, 2023).

Move 1: Step 2 - Topic Generalizations

This section includes statements about the current knowledge, practices, or descriptions of phenomena. The author must discuss recent research as a statement (Hart, 2018). There were 16 introductions that appear to have Step 2 from Move 1.

Examples:

"Peace nowadays seems nowhere to be found. It is something that many people want to achieve not just for themselves but for the world as well, but for some reason, peace seems unattainable." (SocStud2019-2)

"The global trend of adolescent pregnancy is declining, and it could be attributed in part to the integration of sex education into the educational curriculum." (SocStud2019-1)

"We need to take action to improve our communication or conversational skills because this skill is essential toward our daily involvement with the community and globally and to meet the demands of the developing countries." (Eng2018-19)

"Learning the English Language is way distinct compared to learning other academic subjects." (Eng2019-33)

Move 1: Step - 3 Reviewing Items from Previous Research

Examining earlier studies where the writers need to explain or relate results, conclusions, or asserted statements from previous research topics, which would possibly ignite the interest in their study, or sometimes, this information is unusual or interesting to catch the attention of the readers urging them to read until the recommendation part of a research paper (Afshar et al., 2018). Out of 20 introductions, 17 research introductions presented previous research related to the study.

Examples:

"Ang akademikong pag-aaral ay kabilang sa mga pinakamahalagaf pinagmulan ng istres ng mga batang mag-aaral sa buong mundo at lumalabas na itoy medyo malubha sa mga bansa sa Asya (Tang at Westwood, 2007)" (Fil2018-02)

"Academic study is among the most important sources of stress of young students around the world, and it turns out to be a bit serious in Asian countries (Tang at Westwood, 2007)".

"According to Savio and George (2013), communication is a constant procedure is an indispensable element for progress both inside and outside the work environment." (Eng2017-1)

For Move 2, establishing a niche, both Step 1a counterclaiming and Step 1b indicating a gap had one occurrence equivalent to 1.164%, and Step 1d announcing principal findings had six occurrences or 9.83%.

Move 2: Establishing a Niche

Since summarizing the earlier research is a form of a review of related literature, the writer needs to offer some assessment, which happens in establishing the niche. This assessment usually questions the previous study's result as to whether it would be the same as the possible outcome of the current study. In the analyzed introductions, only eight out of 12 writers used to move three.

Move 2: Step - 1a Counterclaiming

This part typically follows move 1, specifically step 3, which examines items of earlier research and is utilized to present a contrasting perspective or show the inadequacies of the earlier research. The thesis's author did not dispute or contest the findings of earlier studies that were published. (Hart, 2018). There was only one introduction, including counterclaiming as part of the introduction.

Example:

“Ngunit kakaunti lamang ang nagbigay atensyon sa pananaliksik na ito kung bibigyang diin ang wikang Filipino.” (Fil2019-4)

“But only a few have paid attention to this research on whether the emphasis is on the Filipino language” (Fil2019-4)

Move 2: Step - 1b Indicating a Gap & 1c Question-Raising

This connects to Move 2 Step 1a, the counterclaiming, and must indicate the unfulfilled niche or a new perspective on the research issue. Move 2 Step 1c question raising includes the questions that may arise about the previous related research included and mentioned in the study. Out of twenty introductions, none indicated a gap or raised questions.

Example:

“We won’t maintain a strategic distance from the boundaries in correspondence, but rather through understanding the hindrances in correspondence and making contemplations in correspondence, we can adequately speak with each other.”

Move 2: Step - 1c Question Raising.

No research included questions about the previous research presented out of twenty studies. According to Afshar, Doosti, and Movassagh (2018), question raising is now considered as part of the move 2 step 1b, indicating a gap. It mentioned that this part can be discussed in the hypothesis’s formation as part of the articles.

Move 2: Step - 1d Continuing a Tradition

Often, this is indicated by causative connectors expressing a need for further research. Six introductions have contained indications for further study to be conducted.

Examples:

“There were so many barriers that need to be considered in terms of communication that leads to ineffective conversation going to misunderstanding” (Eng2017-1)

“Sa pag-aaral na ito ay nais manaliksik na malman at makuha ang mga pananaw ng mg mag-aaral ng Senior High School hinggil sa paggamit ng condom bilang proteksyon sa dulot ng maaagang pagbubuntis na karaniwang ptolema lalong lalo na sa bansang pilipinas at kapag mapaimplimenta na ang pagbibigay ng mga condom sa iba’t-ibang paaralan ng sekondarya particular na sa mga Senior High.” (Fil2017-16)

"In this study, we want to research and get the views of Senior High School students regarding the use of condoms as a protection against early pregnancy, which is a common problem, especially in the Philippines and when the provision of condoms in various secondary schools, particularly in Senior High"

For Move 3, Step 1b Announcing Present Research had nine occurrences, equivalent to 14.75%; Step 2, Announcing Principal Findings, had six occurrences or 9.83%.

Move 3: Occupying the Niche

This is where authors are supposed to fill the gap in move 2. This is where they are supposed to offer a possible solution to their problems. From the 20 C.T.E. introductions, all writers attempted to occupy the gap. From the previous move, there were only eight writers who used it. This is possible because those 12 writers who did not indicate move 2 grounded their gap using move 3. This is where the ambiguity between move two and move 3 becomes apparent, and despite the lack of one, there is still a way to occupy the niche.

Move 3: Step - 1a Outlining Purposes.

The author introduced the problem's resolution stated in Move 2 by stating the study's objectives. None of the research introductions outlined the

goal of the study. Though this was an obligatory part of the research, as mentioned by Swales 1990, the researchers observed that the Purpose of the study is a separate part of the thesis written.

Move 3: Step - 1b Announcing Present Research.

Based on the Swales model describing the Present Research and Outlining the Purpose is highly similar; however, the researchers decided to follow Lakic (1997) because they also saw that there was a difference between the mere presentation of research, which was what in Move 4- Step 1 and outlining purpose was more on the progressive aim of the study. Outlining Purpose can easily be identified with the use of lexemes such as "aims," "will," and "the purpose."

This was an alternative approach used in Move 3 Step 1a, which was the outlining purposes. The author must describe the objectives in terms of what steps to take to achieve the mentioned research objectives.

Examples:

“Sa kadahilanang ito, ang mga mananaliksik ay nagaganyak na alamin kung anong mga salik ang nakaaapekto sa pagkatuto ng pangalawang wika ng tribong mandaya at malaman ang pinaka epektibong motibasyon na maghahatid sa katagumpayan ng pangalawang wika.” (Fil2107-3)

“For this reason, researchers are motivated to find out what factors affect the second language learning of the Mandaya tribe and to know the most effective motivation that will lead to second language success.” (Fil2107-3)

“Therefore, this study must be conducted to contextualize the psychological barriers in communication and to contribute to the academic community of the second language learners.” (Eng2017-1)

Move 3: Step - 2 Announcing Principal Findings

In this part, the researchers must show the most significant findings in the study. This was where previous study results were discussed and reposted as part of the introduction. However, this step does not apply to all disciplines. Five writers used this step to establish principal findings based on the analyzed introductions.

Example:

“Ayon sa pag-aaral ng bansang Seoul, South Korea, ang mag-aaral at guro ay nakararanas ng pagbabahala sa pag-aaral ng pangalawang wika na pangunahing hadlang sa kanilang matagumpay na pagkatuto nito (Yoom, 2012)” (Fil2017-3)

"According to the study of the country of Seoul, South Korea, students and teachers experience anxiety in learning a second language, which is the main obstacle to their successful learning."

“Natuklasan naman sa pag-aaral ni Gonzales (2016), na ang presensya ng inang-wika o katutubong wika mahigit 80,000 mayroon sa Pilipinas ay isa sa mga nagiging dahilan kung bakit mababa ang kagustuhan sa pagkatuto ng unanag wika ng mga mag-aaral.” (Fil2019-4)

"It was discovered in the study of Gonzales (2016) that the presence of the mother tongue or native language of more than 80,000 in the Philippines is one of the reasons why the desire to learn the first language of the students is low"

Move 3: Step 3 Indicating Article Structure

None of the analyzed research introductions contained this step. This denounces the idea of the scientific approach in designing the study. According to Tulud, Mosquera, and Algouti (2021), article structure is a comprehensible

basis of rational planning or process that is bound to be creatively written. This typically introduces how the article will be presented and organized.

Table 2 summarizes the non-conformance of C.T.E. Thesis Introductions based on the CARS Model.

Table 2
Non-conformance of the Thesis Introduction

Moves and Steps		Filipino (9)	English (8)	Social Studies (3)
Move 1 Establishing a Territory				
Step 1	Claiming Centrality	2	1	1
Step 2	Topic Generalizations	5	8	3
Step 3	Reviewing Items from Previous Research	6	9	2
Move 2 Establishing a Niche				
Step 1A	Counterclaiming	1		
Step 1B	Indicating a gap		1	
Step 1C	Question Raising			
Step 1D	Continuing a Tradition	3	3	
Move 3 Occupying a Niche				
Step 1A	Outlining the Purposes			
Step 1B	Announcing Present Research	2	7	
Step 2	Announcing Principal Findings	2	2	2
Step 3	Indicating R.A. Structure			
		21	31	8

Move 1: Establishing a Territory

On *Move 1, Establishing a Territory*, Filipino has 13 non-conformance occurrences; English has 18 non-conformance occurrences; and Social Studies has six non-conformance occurrences.

Move 1: Step 1 Claiming Centrality

“Ang Hindi tamang pag-uugali ay hadlang sa pagkatuto ng mga mag-aaral.” (Fil2018-6)

"Incorrect behavior is a hindrance to students' learning."

"Communications is more important in the twenty-first century than ever before and are more important nowadays." (Eng2017-1)

"In the different fields and research establishments, gender is turning into a concern everywhere throughout the world as it importantly affects the way of learning." (SocStud2017-1)

Move 1: Step 2 Making Topic Generalizations

"Mas mataas ang antas ng pagkatuto ng mga kabataan sa ibang wika kaysa unang wika ayon sa pag-aaral ni Domingo (2017), sa kadahilanang nahuhumaling sila sa pagkatuto ng mga banyagang wika sa pag-aaral mas nagiging matalino sila." (Fil2019-4)

"According to the study of Domingo (2017), the level of learning of young people in other languages is higher than the first language because they are obsessed with learning foreign languages because they think they are becoming smarter."

"Learning the English Language is way distinct compared to learning other academic subjects." (Eng2019-33)

"Peace nowadays seems nowhere to be found. It is something that many people want to achieve not just for themselves but for the world as well, but for some reason, peace seems unattainable." (SocStud2019-2)

Move 1: Step 3 Reviewing Previous Research

"Ang mga gawain tulad ng pagiging hindi handa sa klase, pakikipag-usap sa klase, pakikipaglaban, pandaraya, kawalang-galang sa mga guro, at iba pa ay maaring makagambala sa proseso ng pagtuturo at pag-aaral (Durmuscelebi, 2010)" (Fil2018-6)

"Activities such as being unprepared in class, talking in class, fighting, cheating, disrespecting teachers, and others can disrupt the teaching and learning process."

"The role of English is evident in keeping up this growth and creating talented workforces, which are

all-inclusive compatible (Hamid, 2010)" (Eng2019-29)

"The study of (Bajaj, 2009) stated that most of the instructors/teachers lack confidence in the integrating peace concept in social sciences in a classroom setting." (SocStud2019-2)

This part of the introduction of the thesis needs to conform with the establishing territory. The researcher finds it irrelevant and not worth to be included in the thesis introduction. To be relevant, this part must consist of a topic sentence with supporting ideas that are useful and important (Bawarshi, 2019). This includes the past related result of the research conducted or an observable phenomenon of the researcher. It may also help that this move must discuss the centrality of the topic, general thought, or idea of the phenomenon (Mehrabi et al., 2018).

Move 2: Establishing a Niche

On *Move 2, Establishing a Niche*, Filipino has four non-conformance occurrences; English has four non-conformance occurrences; and Social Studies has no non-conformance occurrences. This move functions as a section having the mini critique due to the fact that the low number of move instances as their reading was limited to identify the niche, gap, or problem found in the previous research (Obeng et al., 2023)

Move 2: Step -1a Counterclaiming

"Ngunit kakaunti lamang ang nagbigay atensyon sa pananaliksik ba ito kung bibgyang diin ang wikang Filipino." (Fil2019-4)

"But few have paid attention to this research on whether the emphasis is on the Filipino language"

Move 2 Step -1b Indicating a Gap.

"We won't maintain a strategic distance from the boundaries in correspondence, but rather through understanding the hindrances in correspondence and making contemplations in correspondence, we can adequately speak with each other." (Eng2020-29)

Move 2: Step -1d Continuing a Tradition

"Dahil sa resulta ng pag-aaral, napagtanto ng mga mananaliksik na tugtugan ang pangangailan sa mga sanggunian na nagtatalakay sa akademikong istres sa mag-aaral ng medyor sa Filipinno ng Unibersidad ng Mindanao." (Fil2018-2)

"Due to the results of the study, the researchers realized that there is a need for references that discuss the academic stress of the Filipino middle school students of the University of Mindanao."

"The researchers have not come across a study that dealt with the influence of teaching strategies in teaching the English language in the local setting." (Eng2019-29)

"There is no quantitative information whatsoever with regards to the perception the preservice teaches and the lower years towards sex education in this institution and her in Davao Region, where it is located where 18 percent of its teenagers are beginning childbearing, the highest nationwide (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2018)" (SocStud2019-1)

These samples included in part of the thesis introduction need to conform to establishing a niche. It only provides proof of the reason why the study must be conducted, but more is required to deepen the Purpose of move 2. This move must show off the weakness of previous studies and show a new approach to explaining, describing, or finding a solution to the existing phenomenon (Mehrabi et al., 2018).

The examples can also be noted using contrastive words, which signifies a gap between the previous. The current studies in which Swales (1990) identified few signals that somehow establish the motivation level of the researchers to carry forward their analysis.

Move 3: Occupying the Niche

On *Move 3, Occupying the Niche*, *Filipino* has four non-conformance occurrences; *English* has nine non-conformance occurrences; and *Social Study* has two non-conformance occurrences.

Move 3: Step -1b Outlining Purposes.

“Sa kadahilanang ito, ang mga mananaliksik ay nagaganyak na alamin ang paniniwala at pag-uugali ng guro na nagtuturo sa mga mag-aaral na may espesyal na pangangailangan.” (Fil2019-7)

“For this reason, researchers are motivated to find out the beliefs and behaviors of teachers who teach students with special needs” (Fil2019-7)

“More so, understanding how the student shifters struggle in their adjustment would inform policymakers and administrators on how to propose programs for these students” (Eng2020-7)

Move 3: Step 2 Announcing Main Findings

“Natuklasan naman sa pag-aaral ni Gonzales (2016), na ang presensya ng inang-wika o katutubong wika mahigit 80,000 mayroon sa Pilipinas ay isa sa mga nagiging dahilan kung bakit mababa ang kagustuhan sa pagkatuto ng unanag wika ng mga mag-aaral.” (Fil2019-4)

“It was discovered in the study of Gonzales (2016) that the presence of the mother tongue or native language of more than 80,000 in the Philippines is one of the reasons why the desire to learn the first language of the students is low.”

“A study showed that there are indeed challenges of using English in constructing text on paper. In the study, the result revealed that 55.6% of the errors found were related to grammar, 42.1% of

mechanical errors, and 2.3% errors were linked to poor constructing of sentences (Amoakohene, 2017)" (Eng2020-5)

"In the Philippines, similar research has been conducted through a mixed approach in the context of catholic educational institutions (Alejo et al., 2014)" (SocStud2019-1)

These were non-conformance of move 3, occupying the niche. This part must be connected to the move 2. The researcher must state the primary goal of the study as the phenomenon described in move 2. The steps to be taken or methods to be used must be mentioned on this move, together with a positive assessment of some part of the mentioned solution. The researcher may also mention the proposed solution or procedure to achieve results and attain the research objectives (Taşpınar & Cubukcu, 2020).

The sum of non-conformance occurrences on these introductions: Filipino has a total of 21; English has 32; and Social Studies 8.

IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

All introductions consist of move 1 establishing a territory and move 3 occupying a niche. Interestingly, many introductions similarly contain Step 2, the Topic Generalizations, and Step 3, the Reviewing Items from Previous Research. A common trend also showed that the previous research was presented through the study's international, national, and local geographical scope. The previous related studies were discussed positively, and the result of the previously conducted study is related to the discussed topic. Additionally,

most of the main topic was introduced in the first paragraph of the introductions. There are some also that the first sentence of the introduction is a definition of a term or defining the variables included in the study.

To effectively establish a territory of the research, the writer must follow all three steps: claiming centrality, making topic generalizations, and reviewing previous research. It is rhetorically comprehensible if the writer states the topic of research that is useful, relevant, important, and worth investigating (Candarli & Jones, 2019). To write this down, it must be presented with a topic sentence and followed with supporting details that show evidence through the previously conducted study. The evidence mentioned must be concerning and related to current knowledge, practice, or phenomenon.

Introductions also showed a lack of interest in explaining the topics further because there was a lack of attempt in Move 2, Establishing a Niche, since there is clear neglect in Move 2, especially in Step 1a counterclaiming, Step 1b Indicating a Gap, and Step 1c Question Raising. But contains somehow Step 1d Continuing Tradition. This is alarming since it shows incompleteness in the introductions. Establishing a niche has a big impact on introducing the topic of the study since it is supposed to explicitly show the opposing viewpoint or the weakness of the previous research as the basis of the current conducted study (Kafes, 2018).

If the writer followed the three steps in move 1, especially step 3, which is reviewing previous research, step 1a in move 2 must be followed (Afshar et al., 2018). Counterclaiming must be included in writing an introduction because this is used to introduce the opposing viewpoints or weaknesses in the previous studies. Then, the writer must proceed directly to step 1b in move 2. Indicating

a gap helps the writer present the new approach, procedure, or solution on how the researcher will tend to address the problem, phenomenon, or knowledge discussed. While step 1c, raising a question can be optional. This will only help the writer to state the opposing viewpoints presented clearly but will not provide a clearer view of how the study will be conducted. Step 1d, continuing a tradition, needs to be included. In this part, the writer must explain why the study must be conducted further. It is possible to employ causative connectors like therefore, hence, consequently, and thus.

The researchers observed that Move 3, Occupying a Niche, specifically Step 1A, Outlining Purposes and Indicating R.A. Structure, was not contained in the 20 introductions since it has separate parts or chapters on the thesis. The researcher also noticed a considerable variation in the pattern of writing introductions in English and Filipino compared to Social Studies. Filipino and English thesis include the centrality of the study conducted while discussing the previous research related to the current study in continuing a tradition. At the same time, Social studies presented centrality and previous research but have yet to establish a niche. Some English and Filipino include Move 1, 2, and 3, while Social Study contains only Move 1 and 3. This implies that the genre of language theses has a different rhetorical characteristic in writing an introduction than social studies.

Move 3: Occupying a niche is important because this will answer the "Why?" question in the study, specifically in step 1a. Outlining purposes must be presented in the introduction of the thesis; the writer must introduce the resolution to the problem by indicating the research objectives. The next step, step 1b, announcing the present study, answers the question of "how? ",

“where?”, and “when?”. This is just an alternative approach to writing. This step must explain the writer's procedure to achieve the research objectives. In including step 3, announcing the main findings, the results must be taken as the most crucial part. However, not all disciplines permit this section to be included in the thesis introduction. Lastly, step 4, evaluation of findings, is often used unless the study aims to develop a new method, such as in the field of science.

Implication for Practice

This implies that the Swales 1990 model will help future researchers to analyze text and construct a model in an organized and complete manner. This will help the U.M. College of Teachers Education evaluate the thesis writing program. Most of the analyzed thesis introductions of the college do not follow a particular format that will unite the department when it comes to writing a thesis introduction since it is a window to each research. This study hopes that the Swales model will be applied as a reference in writing the thesis introduction, and the C.T.E. will conduct an intervention or disciplinary convention to help students write a good thesis introduction.

Implication for Future Research

Swales' model can be used as a reference or guide for researchers when writing a research introduction. Through this, research papers will have standardized quality research introductions that can be useful in the body of knowledge of a discipline and will benefit the community. The researchers must consider the discipline of the study because this may affect the urgency of each

step mentioned on every move of the CARS Model. This may improve the rhetorical structure of research in every discipline. Researchers may conduct a further study on how the Swales model will help the research community achieve a comprehensible and organized rhetorical structure of research.

REFERENCES

- Afshar, H. S., Doosti, M., & Movassagh, H. (2018). A Genre analysis of the introduction section of applied Linguistics and Chemistry research articles. *Iranian Journal of Applied Linguistics (IJAL)*. 21 (1), 163-214.
- Alharbi, Sultan H. (2021). A Comparative genre-based analysis of move-step structure of RAls in two different publication context. *English Language Teaching v14#3*. Doi:10.5539/elt.v14n3p12.
- Caufield, J. (2020). <https://www.scribbr.com/research-paper/research-paper-introduction/>. March 16, 2022.
- Cortes, V. (2013). The purpose of this study is to: Connecting lexical bundles and moves in research article introductions. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 12, 33-43.
- de Britto, F. A., Ferreira, T. C., Nunes, L. P., & Parreiras, F. S. (2021, September). Comparing Supervised Machine Learning Techniques for Genre Analysis in Software Engineering Research Articles. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing (RANLP 2021)* (pp. 63-72).
- Roth, J. A., *The Research Paper: Process, Form, and Content*, 8th Ed., Wadsworth Pub Co., CA., 1999, Pp-161-164 .
<http://readingcraze.com/index.php/writing-style-research-paper/#:~:text=The%20text%20should%20feel%20organized,a%20manner%20that%20creates%20harmony.March> 16, 2022
<https://subjectquery.com/what-is-research/>
- Jam, B. K. (2020). Improving the use of language hedges in academic writing through reading journal articles. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 11(3), 17-23. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.11n.3p.17
- Hyland, K. (2016). *Academic publishing: Issues and challenges in the construction of knowledge*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Kafes, H. (2018). A Genre Analysis of English and Turkish Research Article Introductions. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*. 12(1), 66-79
- Kalali, Nazanin, N., & Kian, Pishkar (2015). Genre analysis and writing skill: Improving iranian EFL learners writing performance through the tenets of genre analysis. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 6(6), 119-130. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/genre-analysis-writing-skill-improving-iranian/docview/2188088756/se-2?accountid=31259>

- Maznun, M.D.B, Roya,M., Vahid, N. (2017) Undergraduate ESL Students' Difficulties in Writing the Introduction for Research Reports. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies; Footscray*. 8 (1), 9-16.
- Mueller, C. (2017). A Comparison of Introductions in Japanese-Authored Japanese Articles, Japanese-Authored English Articles, and Articles by English Native Speakers. *JALT Journal*. 39 (1)
- Moghaddasi, S., & Graves, H. A. B. (2017). "Since Hadwiger's conjecture ... is still open": Establishing a niche for research in discrete mathematics research article introductions. *English for Specific Purposes*, 45, 69-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2016.09.003>
- Ötügen, R., Takkaç, M., & Yağız, O. (2021). Genre analysis in ESP: A review of move analysis models and metadiscourse taxonomies. *e- Kafkas Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8, 67-85. doi:10.30900/kafkasegt.877595 (6) (PDF) *Genre Analysis in ESP: A Review of Move Analysis Models and Metadiscourse Taxonomies 1 Rabia Ötügen 2 Mehmet Takkaç 3 Oktay Yağız 4 ÖAI'de Tür Analizi*. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351287337_Genre_Analysis_in_ESP_A_Review_of_Move_Analysis_Models_and_Metadiscourse_Taxonomies_1_Rabia_Otugen_2_Mehmet_Takkac_3_Oktay_Yagiz_4_OAI'de_Tur_Analizi [accessed Feb 07 2024].
- Pelopida, Agnes. "The Relationship of grade 12 high school students' perceptions of writing self-efficacy and academic writing outcomes in a suburban high school." Order No. 10031621 Johnson & Wales University, 2016. Ann Arbor: *ProQuest*. Web. 16 Mar. 2022.
- Shehzad, W., & Abbas, A. (2016). Genre analysis of generic section headings of MPhil theses' introduction section of linguistics and literature. *NUML Journal of Critical Inquiry*, 14(1), 67-IX. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/genre-analysis-generic-section-headings-mphil/docview/1806173418/se-2?accountid=31259>
- Shirani, S., & Chalak, A. (2018). Genre analysis of iranian TEFL students' master theses. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9(2), 31-37. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.9n.2p.31Tnako, G. (2017). Literary research article abstracts: An analysis of rhetorical moves and their linguistic realizations. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 27, 42-55.
- Suherdi, D., Kurniawan, E., & Lubis, A. H. (2020). A genre analysis of research article 'findings and discussion' sections written by Indonesian undergraduate EFL students. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 10(1), 59-72.

Tulud, D., Mosquera, H. J., & Algouti, M. A. L. T. E. (2021). Methodology Section of Graduate School Thesis Manuscripts: A Genre Analysis Probe of Rhetorical Structure. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 3(9), 36-52.

Yin, B. (2016) An exploratory genre analysis of three graduate degree research proposals in applied linguistics. *Functional linguistics*.

